

PROCESS CONTROL BY REACTION SQUEEZE CASTING FOR INTERMETALLICS-STRENGTHENING OF TiO₂/AL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The metal matrix composites which are fabricated by squeeze casting taking advantage of the reaction between reinforcements and molten metal positively, have been investigated. Since the reactivity between the rutile type of TiO₂ and aluminum changes the severity with the temperature, the three kinds of composites have been fabricated by controlling the temperature conditions of squeeze casting process. One of them is the non-reacted TiO₂/Al composites, second is the reacted homogeneous composites and last is the reacted heterogeneous composites. The hardness of these composites have about 220 Hv, 1100 Hv and 40-1200 Hv, respectively. Furthermore, the hardness of the non-reacted TiO₂/Al composites is adjusted by heat treatment at the temperatures of the solid range of Al, in which the hardness ranges from 220 to 750 Hv in the present experiments.

Keywords: TiO₂, Al, Reaction, MMC, Al₃Ti, Al₂O₃, Intermetallic compound, Squeeze casting

1. INTRODUCTION

Some processes of strengthening of Al alloys have been developed from age hardening since early times to fiber reinforced Al composites nowadays. Currently, new some in-situ processes have been suggested the avail of reaction between matrix alloys and reinforcement or ambient gases. For example, they are SHS(combustion process), Mechanical alloying and subsequent process, Lanxide™, DIMOX™, PRIMEX™^[1,2,3] and Pressureless infiltration process^[4], and they are now remarked, not only strengthening of Al alloys but also fabricating method of ceramics or intermetallic compounds. These processes have some advantages and disadvantages on various view points. Most of them usually take a time or cost, and couldn't get high density materials in many cases, and therefore, they need to be followed by various ways for density, i.g. HIP, pseudo-HIP, or HP. The TiO₂ as reinforcement in composites is employed exceptionally throughout the research of MMC, MA, SHS, or other process^[5,6]. The extensive work on the reaction of the interface of Potassium Titanate Whisker reinforced Al alloys composites by the authors. In the research, it was found that this whisker reacted with Al on the surface at about 600°C except for decomposition at more high temperature^[7]. The crystal structure near surface of this whisker is approximately same to that of TiO₂, and therefore the reactivity of TiO₂/Al composites system has been examined by DTA, which were fabricated by squeeze casting. TiO₂ has three types of structures on the crystal system, which are Anatase, Rutile and Brookite. The rutile type of TiO₂ is employed in this paper to get various kinds of TiO₂/Al composites system ranging from the non-reacted composites to the reacted

strengthened composites by controlling the process conditions of squeeze casting.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The powder of rutile type TiO_2 that was a practical grade of the reagent(WAKO CHEM. IND., LTD) is employed as the reinforcement of the composites, and commercial pure Al(99.993 wt%) as matrix. The chemical compositions of TiO_2 are shown in Table 1. The bulky powder was pressed to a small compaction, and was subsequently sintered at 1100°C for 30 min. Then volume fraction of the preform($45 \times 13.5 \times 18$ mm) is about 40.3%. The preform setting up in the mold(Fig.1), was preheated at a certain temperature($200\text{--}450^\circ\text{C}$) by the furnace with mold from outside. Then molten Al was poured into the mold and immediately pressed with the punch driven by a hydraulic press machine(100 MPa), and then the punch speed was about 10 mm/sec. The composites is fabricated in this procedure by squeeze casting and a part of these composites is heat-treated at the temperature range of $500\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$. To characterize the composites, the indentation hardness test at room and elevated temperatures, the three-point bending test, the observation by OM and SEM and the analysis by EDX, XRD and DTA was carried out.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of employed rutile type TiO_2 (wt%)

Al_2O_3	ZnO	SiO_2	P_2O_5	Na_2O	Nb_2O_5	SO_3	ZrO_2	K_2O	CaO	TiO_2
2.71	1.03	0.56	0.19	0.2	0.15	0.08	0.047	0.01	0.005	bal.

Figure 1. Preparation of TiO_2 preform and schematic illustration of squeeze casting process.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

3.1 Composites structures

The composites fabricated by squeeze casting are distinguished to three types of structures depending on fabricating temperature conditions, which are shown Figure 2. The rectangular part of gray or dark in the white circle is the composite. The microstructures of these composites are shown in Figure 3; (a) is very fine structure, (b) seems to precipitate fine particles and (c) is peculiar just the same as mottled pattern. It is found that the structure of composites is distinctly different depending on the temperature of melt and preform. From the analysis of XRD, SEM-EDX and the hardness, (a) is the non-reacted TiO_2/Al composites whose hardness is about 220 Hv. (b) is the reacted homogeneous composites which are consisted of particulate Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti intermetallic compound matrix, and the hardness is about 1100 Hv homogeneously. Then (c) is the reacted heterogeneous composites, which have complicated structures, are constituted Al, Al_3Ti , Al_2O_3 , and TiO_2 . Here the TiO_2 is sintered, and therefore the hardness of (c) varies from 40 to 1200 Hv. The

Figure 2. Macroscopic photographs of transverse section of three kinds of TiO_2/Al composites. Pouring temperature of melt(P.T.) and temperature of preform(T.P.) are as follows; (a) Non-reacted composites, P.T. : $<700^\circ\text{C}$, T.P. : $<250^\circ\text{C}$
 (b) Reacted homogeneous composites, P.T. : $700\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$, T.P. : $250\text{--}400^\circ\text{C}$
 (c) Reacted heterogeneous composites, P.T. : $>800^\circ\text{C}$, T.P. : $>400^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 3. Optical microstructure of the composites, (a), (b) and (c) in Fig.2.
 (each notation corresponds to that of Fig.2. respectively)

difference of the composites structures is due to the severity of exothermic reaction of reinforcement and matrix aluminum. That is, when molten Al infiltrates into the preform consisting of TiO_2 fine powder, Al reduces TiO_2 and Al itself oxidizes resulting to heat generation. Consequently the temperature of molten Al surrounding TiO_2 ascends and therefore the reaction proceeds more spontaneously. And eventually dissociated Ti dissolves immediately into the melt. In practice, the composites inherit two structures of (b) and (c) when the preform is enlarged in size and infiltrated by molten Al at the moderate temperature conditions, then the outer shell of the composites consists of (b), and the core of (c). In this condition, the change in the temperature of the preform was measured by inserting the sheath thermocouple into a large preform ($\phi 32 \times h25$ mm)(Fig.4). The core's temperature elevates up to over 1400°C in short infiltrating distance, and the structure of this point is the same as (c). The heterogeneous structures of (c) result in sintering of TiO_2 powder when the melt ascends up to high temperature thorough the TiO_2 powders by reaction. That is, the thickness of reacted the homogeneous composites of (b) are limited to about 20 mm. This reacted homogeneous composites are constituted Al_3Ti matrix and dispersed pseudo-particulate Al_2O_3 basically. Thus, these reacted composites are produced in very short time by squeeze casting. Hardness of the reacted homogeneous composites at various elevated temperature are shown in Fig.5. The hardness is lowered with the rise in test temperature, but it is noticed that the hardness of the composites still keeps about 400 Hv at 1000°C .

Figure 4. Temperature transition curves of the preform with molten Al infiltrated resulting to the reacted heterogeneous composites. The positions of thermocouple are as follows; ① outside of preform, ② case in preform, ③ core in preform.

Figure 5. Hardness of the reacted homogeneous composites at elevated temperature

3.2 Heat treatment of non-reacted composites

It is supposed that the hardness of non-reacted composites will be adjusted by heat treatment. Figure 6 shows the hardness distributions of non-reacted composites from infiltrating surface after heat treatment at each temperature. The hardness increases with the temperature of heat treatment and particularly noteworthy is the hardness change at 500°C and 600°C, because the temperature is in solid phase range of matrix. The second remarkable point is the variable hardness distribution near the surface on temperature range of liquidus phase of Al matrix. There is thin soft layer 220 Hv about 10 μm, and then the hardness abruptly increased and gradually decreased a little forward to inside. In the case of 800°C, there can be seen the step of hardness, which means that there is the alteration on the composition.

From the analysis of XRD, the reaction products of composites are identified as Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti compound, and the quantity of the products increases with rise in temperature of heat treatment. Of course, there exists Al, too, and it decreases with the reaction progress. Figure 7 shows the X-ray line analysis of the composites near the boundary. Considering these results, it appears that Al penetrates into the composites by heat treatment of liquid phase. This is the phenomenon attributed

Figure 6. Hardness distribution of the non-reacted composites from surface after heat treatment at various temperatures.

Figure 7. X-ray line analysis of the non-reacted composites after heat treatment at various temperatures. (a) as cast, (b) 600°C-1h, (c) 700°C-1h, (d) 800°C-1h.

to the reaction. The following chemical equations are derived from the reactive products. The change of free energy of equation (1) is gotten $\Delta G = -34.0$ kJ/mol at 600°C from calculations, and therefore the reaction proceeds sufficiently.

Eq.(1) accompanies with decrease in volume about 13.6%. This causes the influx of Al into the composites. TiO_2 of the surface is reduced by inflow Al, and surface layer is changed to $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites eventually. At that time, the reduced Ti dissolved molten Al, and flow into inside of the

Figure 8. Hardness of the non-reacted composites at elevated temperature and subsequent hardness change with isothermal heat treatment of 600°C.

composites with rising temperature. Eq.(2) is the case of this experiment. Basically, what kind of reaction product in Al-Ti intermetallics is produced, is determined by the stoichiometric quantity of reduced Ti and in situ Al. In the experiment, the composites is eventually constituted of Al_3Ti matrix and dispersed particulate Al_2O_3 .

Figure 8 shows the hardness of the non-reacted composites at elevated temperatures, and the change in hardness of the composites at 600°C. The reaction of the composites comparatively proceeds slowly, so it is easy to very control the hardness. The hardness of the composites attains to 750 Hv and saturates. According to the bending test, the composites showed the bending strength of about 550 Mpa.

3.3 DTA OF NON-REACTED COMPOSITES

From ascribed before, it is evident that the reactivity between TiO_2 (rutile) and Al plays a significant role in occurrence of these three composites and hardening of non-reacted composites. Figure 9 shows DTA of non-reacted composites. It is noticed that the exothermic reaction exists before and after at melting point of Al. From the results, the reacted composites is due to the reaction above m.p. of Al, and the hardening of non-reacted composites is due to the reaction below m.p. of Al. It is considered that the temperature producing the non-reacted composites do not attain

Figure 9. Differential thermal analysis of the non-reacted composites.

to the temperature conditions of exothermic reaction above the m.p. of Al. Then, from the result of slow rate (3 °C/min), it is clear that the exothermic reaction above the m.p. of Al does not begin due to fusion of Al, but the exothermic reaction begins and afterward the fusion of Al occurs in mid course.

The TiO₂/Al composites fabricated by squeeze casting is practically prospective for the strengthening of Al alloys, and for the fabricating method of Al₂O₃ dispersed Al₃Ti matrix composites too. However, the trial experiment showed that employing powder metallurgy method failed to prepare the composites. The possible reason of that is caused by oxidation on the interface of reinforcement and matrix alloy.

Through the experiments, there may be the critical temperature of molten aluminum and preform as well as the critical volume fraction of TiO₂ powder. They are important process parameters to be solved. The basic understanding of reaction mechanism is also important. Now they are future issues, remarkably interested in.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

It is revealed that the squeeze casting process of rutile type TiO₂ and Al produces the three kinds of composites with different micro structure and hardness, depending on the temperature conditions. One of them is the non-reacted composites, second is the reacted homogeneous composites, and last is the reacted heterogeneous composites. The reacted homogeneous composites inherit about 1100 Hv in the hardness at room temperature and hold 400 Hv at 1000°C. The hardness of non-reacted composites are adjusted by heat treatment, ranging from 220 Hv to 750 Hv at the temperature of 500 to 600°C.

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